

A guide to selecting high-performing renewable antibodies for GEF-H1 across western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

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Abstract

GEF-H1 is a Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor involved in cytoskeletal organization, cell signaling, and neural development. We characterized eleven commercially available research antibodies against GEF-H1 for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized workflow. Antibody performance was assessed by comparing signals in a wild-type cell line and its corresponding knockout derivative. This work is part of a broader collaborative public-good initiative to improve biomedical research by systematically evaluating commercial antibodies against human proteins and openly sharing the data as a resource for the scientific community. We encourage readers to use this report as a guide for selecting antibodies best suited to their specific applications.

Keywords:

UniProt ID Q92974, *ARHGEF2*, GEF-H1, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

The GEF-H1 protein, encoded by the *ARHGEF2* gene, plays a central role in cytoskeletal organization, cell polarity, mitotic spindle formation, and neuronal differentiation through activation of RhoA signaling pathways (1). The protein functions primarily by catalyzing the exchange of GDP for GTP on Rho family GTPases, thereby regulating downstream signaling involved in microtubule dynamics and actin remodeling (2). Altered *ARHGEF2* expression or function has been linked to several human diseases, including neurodevelopmental disorders, cancer progression, and inflammatory conditions (3).

Here, we characterized eleven antibodies against GEF-H1, for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using standardized protocols. Antibody performance was assessed by comparing signal in wild-type (WT) and knockdown (KD) cells. The resulting data can guide the selection of antibodies best suited to specific research needs, enabling robust biochemical and cellular assessment of the target.

This work is part of a broader collaborative initiative involving academics, funders, and antibody manufacturers, aimed at improving biomedical research reproducibility through the systematic characterization of commercial antibodies against human proteins and open data sharing. Antibodies are provided in-kind by participating manufacturers. The approach involves identifying cell lines with sufficient target expression, generating or sourcing corresponding knockout or KD cell lines, and evaluating commercially available antibodies, with a focus on renewable (monoclonal and recombinant) reagents (4). We do not provide explicit antibody recommendations; rather, the data are presented to enable independent interpretation. Guidance on data interpretation is available via the YCharOS gateway (5) and in Table 5 of this data note.

Results and discussion

Antibody performance was assessed by comparing readouts from control (ctrl) and KD cells (4). In the absence of commercially available KO cell lines, small interfering RNA (siRNA) can be used to KD the target gene, serving as a negative control. To this end, we examined the DepMap transcriptomics database (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) to identify cell lines with expression levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), a threshold we have found to be suitable (6). The U-87 MG cell line, which expresses *ARHGEF2* at $6.0 \log_2$ (TPM+1), was selected (Table 1) based on its expression of the target, favorable morphology (large, flat cells), and prior use demonstrating efficient knockdown. Moreover, according to DepMap, U-87 MG does not harbor mutations in *ARHGEF2* that could affect antibody-epitope binding. A non-targeting control siRNA pool was used to treat U-87 MG ctrl cells, while *ARHGEF2* was KD using a pool of siRNA targeting this gene.

Primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 2, with usage conditions summarized in Table 3 and secondary antibodies in Table 4. Antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios to align with manufacturer recommendations and account for proprietary formulations.

All eleven antibodies were first tested in western blot using ctrl and *ARHGEF2* KD protein lysates (Figure 1). This step enables concurrent validation of the KD cell line (absence of detectable GEF-H1 signal) and identification of antibodies that detect GEF-H1 with a band that is absent in the KD lane. Dilutions were selected based on supplier recommendations and adjusted when necessary (Table 3).

The ability of each antibody to capture GEF-H1 from U-87 MG WT lysates was assessed by immunoprecipitation followed by western blot analysis (Figure 2). Each immunoprecipitation was performed using 2 µg of antibody (Table 3). Starting material (SM), unbound (UB), and immunoprecipitate (IP) fractions were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and probed using antibody ab201687** identified in the western blot screen. This assay evaluates target capture but does not assess selectivity (i.e., binding to GEF-H1 versus off-target proteins).

For immunofluorescence, antibodies were screened at two dilutions using a mosaic strategy in which ctrl and KD cells, pre-labelled with distinct dyes, were imaged within the same field of view to minimize experimental bias (Figure 3). Antibodies were tested at supplier-recommended dilutions when available; otherwise, they were tested at 1 and 2 µg/mL (Table 3). Because detergent choice can strongly influence staining depending on protein subcellular distribution (7), both saponin and Triton X-100 were evaluated.

Signal was quantified across at least 500 ctrl and KD cells (4), and representative images are shown in Figure 3. For each antibody, the ctrl/KD signal intensity ratio is reported: values near 1 indicate comparable signal in ctrl and KD cells, values >1 indicate enrichment in ctrl cells, and values <1 indicate higher signal in KD cells. The value shown corresponds to the experimental condition yielding the highest ratio. These ratios facilitate comparison under the conditions tested but should be interpreted within the context of the specific assay and cell type.

In summary, we screened eleven commercially available GEF-H1 antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing signal in ctrl and *ARHGEF2* KD in U-87 MG cells. To assist with data interpretation, Table 5 outlines common antibody performance scenarios across applications. High-quality renewable antibodies detecting GEF-H1 were identified for each application. Researchers studying GEF-H1 in other species are encouraged to consider these results and verify predicted species reactivity with the manufacturer before proceeding.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. First, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all available antibodies against any given targets. While YCharOS partners provide access to the majority of renewable antibodies, some widely used polyclonal antibodies may not be included.

Second, the YCharOS approach is protein-agnostic and aims to provide objective data on antibody performance without predefined expectations regarding molecular weight or localization. As such, only a brief overview of the protein target is provided, and expert interpretation of banding patterns and subcellular localization is encouraged.

Third, experiments are not performed in biological replicates due to the parallel testing of multiple antibodies recognizing distinct epitopes. The identification of at least one specific antibody supports target expression in WT cells and its absence in KD cells, providing a reference for evaluating other antibodies. Experiments are performed using standardized conditions and master mixes to minimize variability. In immunofluorescence, testing at multiple antibody concentrations provides an additional assessment of specificity. Experiments may be repeated when no signal is detected. Furthermore, these data are generated independently of manufacturers' validation processes, effectively constituting an external replication.

Finally, conclusions are limited to the experimental conditions and cell line used. The reliance on a single cell type represents a constraint, as protein expression levels can influence antibody performance. The use of cancer cell lines also introduces potential confounders, including mutations that may affect antibody-epitope binding. These limitations are inherent to cell line-based validation approaches.

Method

The standardized protocols used for this antibody characterization study were established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers, and antibody manufacturers (4). Brief descriptions of the experimental procedures used in this study are described below.

Cell lines

The cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1. To facilitate proper citation and unambiguous identification, all cell lines and antibodies are referenced with their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (8). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

The cell lines used in this study are listed in Table 1. To facilitate unambiguous identification and proper citation, all resources are referenced using their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) (8, 9). All cell lines used in this study were regularly tested for mycoplasma contamination and were confirmed to be mycoplasma-free.

U-87 MG ctrl cells were treated with the ON-TARGETplus Non-targeting Control Pool (Horizon Discovery (cat. number. D-001810-10). To knockdown *ARHGEF2*, U-87 MG cells were treated with the *ARHGEF2* SMARTPool from Horizon Discovery (cat. number L-009883-00-0005) for five days. Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 13778030) was used to transfect the siRNA following the manufacturer's protocol.

Primary and secondary antibodies

Primary antibodies are listed in Table 2 with RRIDs (9). Working dilutions for western blot and immunofluorescence, and volumes corresponding to 2 µg input for immunoprecipitation, are provided in Table 3. Secondary antibodies and their working concentrations are listed in Table 4. Antibody usage is reported as dilution ratios.

Antibody screening by western blot

U-87 MG ctrl and *ARHGEF2* KD cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 78427). Lysates were briefly sonicated, incubated on ice for 30 min. Lysates were spun at ~110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C, and 30 µg of protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Protein separation was performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) followed by transfer on nitrocellulose membranes. Total protein transfer was confirmed by Ponceau S

staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10). Membranes were blocked in 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). After washing, membranes were incubated with peroxidase conjugated secondary antibodies for 1 hr at room temperature. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). All tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

U-87 MG WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 1 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

U-87 MG ctrl and *ARHGEF2* KD cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). Ctrl and KD cells were plated in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Culture medium was removed, and cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 47746S) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL) for 10 min at room temperature. Cells were permeabilized in PBS1x with 0.05% Saponin (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 47036) or 0.1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature. Cells were blocked in IF buffer (PBS1x, 5% BSA, 0.005% Saponin or 0.01% Triton X-100) with 5% normal goat (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) serum for 1 hr at room temperature. Cells were incubated with the corresponding IF buffer containing the primary GEF-H1 antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with the corresponding Coralite plus 555-conjugated secondary antibody in IF buffer for 1 hr at room temperature. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with PBS1x then incubated with DAPI for 3 min (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) and washed once with PBS1x.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.94 air objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI,

Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (11). We have developed a collection of scripts in Python and in ImageJ/FIJI made openly available on GitHub (https://github.com/ABIF-McGill/YCharOS_IF_characterization) (4). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Data availability

Underlying data

Dataset for the GEF-H1 antibody screening study <to be submitted>

Data are available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0).

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Competing interests

For this project, the authors developed partnerships with leading antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to this project at no cost. These partners include: Abbexa, Abcam, ABCD antibodies, ABclonal, Aviva Systems Biology, BioTechne, Cell Signaling Technology, Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank, GeneTex, Horizon Discovery (Revvity), MilliporeSigma, Proteintech, Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	HTB-14	CVCL_0022	U-87 MG	WT

Table 2: Summary of the GEF-H1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abbexa	abx422627**	A2511652Q	AB_3739799	recombinant mono	J175	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab155785	1099750-14	AB_2818944	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.71	Wb, IP, IF
Abcam	ab201687**	1121851-1	AB_3740827	recombinant mono	EPR17963	rabbit	0.59	Wb, IF, other
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP59669_P050	QC30631-40645	AB_10880757	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP84595_P050	QC60787-42921	AB_3740825	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
GeneTex	GTX125893	45476	AB_11177391	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.71	Wb, IP, IF
GeneTex	GTX629398*	41323	AB_2888104	monoclonal	GT336	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX641355**	45663	AB_3740826	recombinant mono	HL3470	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Proteintech	24472-1-AP	00082122	AB_2879560	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF, other
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-34750**	79532277	AB_2848658	recombinant mono	JG36-46	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF, other
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-53442**	79532377	AB_3247913	recombinant mono	23GB3675	rabbit	0.60	Wb, other

Wb=western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody

Table 3: Dilutions of GEF-H1 antibodies used in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Catalog number	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendor-recommended Wb dilution	Wb dilution used	IP volume (µL, for 2 µg input)	Vendor-recommended IF dilution	IF dilution tested (1)	IF dilution tested (2)	IF dilution shown
abx422627**	1.00	1/500 - 1/2000	1/1000	2.0	1/25 - 1/200	1/500	1/1000	1/1000
ab155785	0.71	1/500 - 1/3000	1/1000	2.8	1/100 - 1/1000	1/500	1/700	1/700
ab201687**	0.59	1/2000	1/2000	3.4	1/500	1/250	1/500	1/500
ARP59669_P050	0.50	1/500 - 1/2500	1/500	4.0	-	1/250	1/500	1/500
ARP84595_P050	0.50	1/500	1/500	4.0	-	1/250	1/500	1/500
GTX125893	0.71	1/500 - 1/3000	1/1000	2.8	1/100 - 1/1000	1/500	1/700	1/700
GTX629398*	1.00	1/500 - 1/3000	1/500	2.0	1/50 - 1/1000	1/50	1/1000	1/1000
GTX641355**	1.00	1/500 - 1/3000	1/1000	2.0	-	1/500	1/1000	1/1000
24472-1-AP	1.00	1/500 - 1/2000	1/1000	2.0	1/200 - 1/800	1/400	1/1000	1/1000
MA5-34750**	1.00	1/500 - 1/2000	1/500	2.0	1/50 - 1/200	1/100	1/1000	1/1000
MA5-53442**	0.60	1/1000 - 1/5000	1/2000	3.3	1/50 - 1/1000	1/600	1/1000	1/1000

Table 4: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM001	AB_3068333	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.5
Cell Signaling Technology	Protein A, HRP conjugate	12291	NA	polyclonal	0.125	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR003	AB_3073507	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5
Proteintech	CoraLite Plus 555-Goat Anti-Mouse Antibody (H+L)	RGAM003	AB_3068539	recombinant polyclonal	0.5	0.5

Table 5: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein detected (arrowhead)</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others</p>	<p>Unsuccessful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein not detected</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>SM UB IP</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein captured in the IP</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>SM UB IP</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein captured in the IP</p>	<p>Unsuccessful antibody</p> <p>SM UB IP</p> <p>245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein not captured in the IP</p>	<p>WT/KO cell mosaic</p>	<p>Successful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>Target protein detected (white staining)</p>	<p>Unsuccessful antibody</p> <p>WT KO</p> <p>Target protein not detected</p>

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Figure 1: GEF-H1 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: GEF-H1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: GEF-H1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (1/2)

Figure 3: GEF-H1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (2/2)

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: GEF-H1 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates from U-87 MG ctrl and *ARHGEF2* KD cells were prepared and analyzed in western blot using the indicated GEF-H1 antibodies. Ponceau-stained membranes are shown to confirm equal loading and efficient protein transfer from gel to membrane. Predicted band size: 111 kDa. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 2: GEF-H1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

U-87 MG WT lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using the indicated GEF-H1 antibodies. Immunoprecipitates were analyzed by western blot using the GEF-H1 antibody ab201687** (1/1000). Ponceau-stained membranes are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.

Figure 3: GEF-H1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

U-87 MG ctrl and *ARHGEF2* KD cells were pre-labelled with green and far-red fluorescent dyes, respectively, mixed at a 1:1 ratio, and plated in 96-well plates. Cells were permeabilized with saponin or Triton X-100 and stained with the indicated GEF-H1 antibodies. Representative images of the antibody and DAPI channels (grayscale) are shown. WT and KD cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Ctrl/KD ratios are indicated in the top-left corner of each antibody channel image. Scale bar = 10 μ m. **= recombinant antibody, *= monoclonal antibody.